

Corrosion testing of solar cells: Wear-out degradation behavior

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ABSTRACT

Corrosion is one of the main end-of-life degradation and failure modes in photovoltaic (PV) modules. However, it is a gradual process and can take many years to become a major risk factor because of the slow accumulation of water and acetic acid (from encapsulant ethylene vinyl acetate (EVA) degradation). In this work, an accelerated aging test for acetic acid corrosion was developed to probe wear-out and end-of-life behavior and facilitate screening of new cell, passivation, metallization, and interconnection technologies. In the tests, the top glass and EVA layers were removed from PV modules to expose the solar cells and interconnects. These “opened” modules were then placed in acid baths under varying conditions, including acid concentration, temperature, and electrical bias. Three cell technologies were tested, including Al-back surface field (BSF), passivated emitter and rear contact (PERC), and silicon heterojunction (SHJ). For all conditions, the presence of acid accelerated module power loss compared to control tests with water baths. Increased temperature accelerated the rate of degradation by several times. Application of electrical bias led to an initial drop in short circuit current, but these modules eventually outperformed the non-biased modules. In all tests, lead oxides were the primary degradation products detected, and found to accumulate mostly along the printed metallization, especially in proximity to the busbar. SHJ cells with a silver paste-based interconnection outperformed Al-BSF and PERC cells with a solder-based interconnection. The accelerated corrosion test methods can be optimized to match corrosion behavior observed in field modules with greater precision and shorter times than standard damp heat tests, and is especially useful to assess the long-term durability of the continuously increasing variety of corrosion sensitive PV materials and components.

1. Introduction

The lifetime of a photovoltaic (PV) module is influenced by a variety of degradation and failure phenomena. While there are several performance and accelerated aging tests to assess design quality and early- or mid-life failure modes, there are few to probe the mechanisms and impacts of end-of-life degradation modes such as corrosion. There are a variety of components in PV cells and modules that may be susceptible to corrosion, including solar cell passivation, metallization, and interconnection. The materials, processes, and designs of these components are continuously evolving, so tools and tests to assess their corrosion behavior are especially important in product development. The damp heat test is the main accelerated test for corrosion in PV modules [1–4]. However, the conditions are very aggressive – 85 °C and 85% relative humidity – and may overstress modules, inducing degradation that is

not observed in field operation [5]. Moreover, the test only includes water as a chemical stressor, even though it is known that acetic acid is present in field modules in concentrations up to at least 0.13% v/v (vol/vol) after several years [5,6]. Therefore a more accurate test for corrosion in PV modules should include acetic acid as a stressor and be performed at lower temperatures [1,2].

Acetic acid in modules is generated by the degradation of ethylene vinyl acetate (EVA) encapsulants, and it can take several years to accumulate to appreciable levels above the solar cells [5–8]. This is because the degradation of EVA is an autocatalytic process, and the rates of generation and accumulation of degradation products such as acetic acid are not linear with time. At first it will increase slowly, and then rapidly, with the module performance decreasing correspondingly [1,2,9]. In the damp heat test it can take 3000 h or more for appreciable amounts of acetic acid to accumulate [10,11]. Highly accelerated tests

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may achieve degradation faster, but extrapolation of test results to field performance remains a challenge [12,13]. Kyranaki et al. and Tanahashi et al. [1,2,14] have developed acetic acid-based corrosion tests for solar cells that are much shorter in duration, the former by bath immersion and the latter by vapor exposure. They both observe mostly current and fill factor losses, but propose two different mechanisms, either solder or finger corrosion. Finger corrosion was also studied by Kraft et al., who exposed solar cells to acid before soldering on ribbon wires [15]. They observed preferential oxidation of lead in the printed metallization frit. Additionally, the variety of test variables means that methods must be optimized to produce meaningful results, ideally to match corrosion behavior observed in field modules (e.g. as in Refs. [16,17]).

In this work, an accelerated corrosion test method was developed based on the immersion of modules into acetic acid baths. Single cell modules had the top glass/EVA removed after lamination so that only the front-side of the cells and interconnects were exposed, since this is where the highest concentration of acetic acid can be expected. Three test conditions were varied, including acetic acid concentration, temperature, and electrical bias. Tests were performed on modules with three different cell technologies, including aluminum-back surface field (Al-BSF), passivate emitter and rear contact (PERC), and silicon heterojunction (SHJ). The test to failure methodology developed in this work can be used on a variety of cell, passivation, metallization, and interconnection technologies to assess and compare their corrosion susceptibility, especially their end-of-life behavior. Ultimately, this would feed into more robust and reliable design of these materials and technologies by greatly reducing test time with respect to outdoor monitoring or damp heat testing.

2. Experimental

2.1. Module fabrication

Single cell monocrystalline silicon modules with Al-BSF, PERC, or SHJ solar cells were prepared with a half-laminated or “open” structure as illustrated in Fig. 1a. The laminate structure included glass front and back covers and an ethylene vinyl acetate (EVA) encapsulant. An ethylene tetrafluoroethylene (ETFE) release layer was placed between the solar cell and top layer EVA so that it formed a weakly adhered interface [18]. After lamination, the top layer glass/EVA/ETFE was pried off the module, resulting in a half-laminated construction that leaves the cell, metallization, and interconnects exposed for the corrosion tests. In this work only the front of the cell was exposed to acid because comparatively little acetic acid forms in the dark area behind solar cells. However, with increased use of bifacial cells, similar tests on the back of solar cells would also be of interest. The glass/EVA/cell structure also ensured the cells were flat and able to be handled without breakage during the tests. The solar cell top metallization was based on

screen printed silver with five (Al-BSF and PERC) or four (SHJ) busbars, and cell interconnects were 1.5 mm wide flat copper wires coated with a lead-tin based solder. For Al-BSF and PERC cells these were soldered onto the busbars, and for SHJ cells they were attached using a silver-based electrically conductive adhesive (ECA).

2.2. Corrosion testing

Modules were immersed in acetic acid baths using the conditions shown in Table 1. The three test variables included acid concentration (0%–10% v/v), temperature (20 °C or 60 °C), and cell electrical bias (0 A or 8.5 A). These stress levels were selected to mimic or intensify field conditions. Pure (i.e. deionized) and mineral (i.e. ionized) water were used as control conditions. As for acetic acid, field modules have been measured containing up to 0.13% v/v acid [5,6], and in this work higher concentrations were also used to accelerate corrosion processes. For simplification, in the rest of this work acid concentrations are referred to as percentages, instead of % v/v. For temperature, 60 °C is a typical field module operating temperature in temperate climates [19]. Finally, for electrical bias, 8.5 A corresponds approximately to the max power point current of the solar cells under AM1.5 illumination.

The baths and modules were placed inside of stainless steel trays and covered during the tests to minimize evaporation of the acid solutions. For the elevated temperatures, hot plates were used to heat the solutions. For biasing, the modules were connected to a power supply as seen in Fig. 1b and left in the dark. During the development of the test methodology not all possible combinations of conditions were explored.

2.3. Module and material characterization

Periodically during the corrosion tests the modules were removed from their solutions, rinsed, and dried before being characterized. Modules were visually inspected, and then light current-voltage (I–V) characteristics were measured under AM1.5 conditions. The main optoelectronic properties that were monitored included the power at maximum power point (P_{MPP}), short circuit current (I_{SC}), open circuit voltage (V_{OC}), and fill factor (FF). After these tests, the modules were reintroduced to their acid baths. Corrosion tests were carried out for up

Table 1

Accelerated corrosion test variables and levels. Not all combinations of levels were tested.

Variable	Level or condition
Acid conc. [% v/v]	0 (pure or mineral), 0.1, 1, 5, 10
Temperature [°C]	20, 60
Electrical bias [A]	0, 8.5
Cell technology	Al-BSF, PERC, SHJ

Fig. 1. Cross-sectional schematic of half-laminated module construction after lamination (a, left) and after removal of the top layers (a, right) (dimensions not to scale), and photograph of the accelerated corrosion test setup for high temperature and electrical bias (b).

to 600 h of total exposure (n.b. compared to >3000 h for noticeable corrosion effects in damp heat testing) [1,4,11].

For some tests, small specimens up to $2 \times 2 \text{ cm}^2$ were cut for optical and scanning electron microscopy (SEM) to examine changes to cell and metallization microstructure. Identification of degradation product composition and phase was done by energy dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDX) at 15 kV acceleration voltage and Raman spectroscopy with 514 nm excitation.

3. Results and discussion

Most of the tests in this work utilized Al-BSF cells. Many advanced solar cell technologies (e.g. PERC) utilize similar front metallization and interconnect materials, based on printed silver pastes and soldered interconnects. Thus, Al-BSF cells were used to establish a baseline for developing the test methods. Some tests were performed on PERC and SHJ solar cells, specifically, unbiased at 60 °C with water, 0.1%, and 1% acid.

3.1. Al-BSF modules

3.1.1. Visual inspection

The visual aspect of the modules underwent significant change over the course of the tests. Most notable was a discoloration of the acid exposed modules (Fig. 2a). This likely came from accumulation on the surface of corrosion products, such as lead oxides, which can be yellow, brown, or red in color depending on their oxidation state and layer thickness. In the high acid concentration tests (>1%) ribbon detachment was fairly common (Fig. 2b), a behavior also observed in Ref. [1]. This detachment failure tended to occur before significant degradation was observed (i.e. >5% change in optoelectronic properties), so the remainder of the corrosion tests used water, 0.1%, or 1% acid. After extended exposure the solder on the cell and string interconnect ribbons began corroding away, even leaving the copper core exposed. Thus by visual inspection it appeared that the solder joint to the busbar was the cell component most likely to fail, a finding consistent with the lower oxidation potentials of lead-tin solder compared to copper and silver [16]. While lead-tin was the only solder used in these tests, one can assume that some lead-free solders may have similar susceptibility to corrosion. For example, solders containing zinc, indium, or bismuth have been found to be more susceptible to corrosion than lead-tin solder [20,21]. In contrast, solders with silver or copper are more resistant than lead-tin solders.

3.1.2. Electrical performance

Fig. 3 shows the evolution of normalized maximum power (P_{MPP}) and fill factor (FF) over time for some of the Al-BSF module tests,

Fig. 3. Normalized maximum single-cell module power as a function of exposure time for water and acid (0.1% and 1%) exposed Al-BSF cells at 20 °C and 60 °C, with and without electrical bias. Inset shows FF for the same tests.

including water and acid (0.1% and 1%). Other cell parameters (I_{SC} , V_{OC}) are not shown. Max cell power was the main value that changed, caused mostly by reductions in the fill factor (FF). Short circuit current (I_{SC}) generally did not change significantly. Open circuit voltage (V_{OC}) was relatively stable for all tests, not decreasing more than 3% of their initial values. This contrasts other reports from the damp heat test (85 °C and 85% relative humidity), where water is the main stressor and FF, V_{OC} and I_{SC} losses have been observed [1,2,4]. For other acetic acid tests [1,2], FF and I_{SC} losses have been observed, mostly in line with these results. These differences may arise from the different cell technologies or test conditions.

As for the effect of acid concentration, in all tests, the presence of acid accelerated module degradation compared to the water tests. In fact, power loss was less than 10% for water tests in any test conditions, even up to 600 h of exposure. Moreover, the type of water, pure or mineral, resulted in no differences in performance. The initial rate of power loss was similar for acid concentrations from 1% to 10% (not shown), indicating that acetic acid was not a rate-limiting reactant for these accelerated conditions. In 0.1% acid the rates were slower, reaching 60% initial power in more than twice the time as 1% acid modules ($\approx 600 \text{ h}$ vs. $\approx 250 \text{ h}$ respectively). Ribbon detachment eventually occurred in all tests with acid concentration above 1%. When detachment occurred, cell power would drop by tens of percent, and even to zero in the most severe cases, similar to behavior in Ref. [1]. Because of this, it was not possible to decouple gradual corrosion effects

Fig. 2. Visual inspection of Al-BSF modules during the corrosion tests, showing discoloration (a) and detachment of cell interconnect ribbons (b).

with this sudden detachment. Considering this ribbon detachment, further optimization of the test method focused acid concentrations $\leq 1\%$.

As for the effect of bath temperature, increasing temperature (60 °C versus 20 °C) resulted in a much faster rate of power loss. After 300 h modules in the low temperature tests had undergone about 4% power loss, compared to nearly 50% for modules in the high temperature tests. Even up to nearly 600 h the modules at low temperature had only lost 9% of their initial power. As chemical corrosion is an electrochemical process, corrosion is thermally activated, thus corrosion rates would be accelerated during the daytime when modules are warmest.

As for the effect of electrical bias, the application of bias to the cells resulted in a rapid reduction in short circuit current (about 8%) in the first few hours of exposure. After this, current remained stable, and fill factor losses became the main contributor to power loss. These modules outperformed the unbiased modules up to 300 h, with power loss of only 20%, compared to 50%. Because corrosion is an electrochemical process, it was expected that an electrical bias would alter the mechanism and rate of power loss. Electroplating of copper on the silver metallization was observed on the biased cells, and this process may have improved connection to the cell interconnect wires, thereby contributing to the better performance over the unbiased cells.

3.1.3. Material-level characterization

SEM was used to examine the cell microstructure during the tests. The most notable feature included accumulation and growth of microstructures along the printed metallization, a feature also observed in field modules [16,17]. In water these had a flake-like morphology (Fig. 4a), while in acid they exhibited a fine, cluster-like morphology (Fig. 4b). EDX showed these features to be rich in lead and oxygen and their Raman spectra (Fig. 4c) showed characteristic peaks of PbO₂, most notably in the region from 120 to 160 cm⁻¹ [22]. Peak shape and position sometimes varied by point, which may be a laser-induced heating effect of the structures with low crystal quality, similar to behavior observed in Ref. [22]. Metal acetates and other oxides were not detected at any points.

3.2. PERC and SHJ modules

PERC cells have rapidly become the dominant technology in the PV market. The front structure and metallization are similar to Al-BSF cells, with silver-based metallization and soldered interconnects. The back structure is different, with a passivated rear contact (with Al₂O₃ or SiN_x layers), but because of the half-laminated construction of the modules it is not exposed in these corrosion tests. Indeed, in a bifacial configuration with a glass/glass structure, one can expect accumulation of acetic acid on the back of the cells, so similar tests on both sides of the cell would be interesting in future work to distinguish the effects [4].

Fig. 4. SEM along the finger of solar cells exposed at 20 °C in water (a) and 1% acid (b), and Raman spectra of corrosion products in acid exposed cells indicating the presence of lead oxides (c).

SHJ solar cells are a high efficiency technology based on crystalline silicon coated on both sides with layers of amorphous silicon and transparent conductive oxides. The amorphous silicon passivates the cell surface, giving rise to higher cell voltages than for Al-BSF or PERC cells. Typically, cell interconnect ribbons are attached with an ECA instead of solder, because the thin amorphous silicon layers can be sensitive to the high soldering process temperatures.

For PERC and SHJ the visual appearance during testing was similar to the Al-BSF modules (Fig. 2), with discoloration of the acid exposed modules. Normalized power versus test time for Al-BSF, PERC, and SHJ modules is shown in Fig. 5 in 1% acid. Fill factor was the main parameter linked to power loss, shown in the inset. In water no significant corrosion was observed for any cell type (not shown). The behavior between Al-BSF and PERC was very similar throughout the tests, as may be expected because of their similar front structure. Thus, despite improvements in device structure for PERC to increase efficiency, they still remain susceptible to the corrosion phenomena that occur in Al-BSF technologies. As for SHJ, the initial rate of power loss was similar up to 150 h (about 10%), but after this the Al-BSF and PERC cells degraded much more quickly. After 300 h the Al-BSF and PERC cells had lost 50% of their initial power, compared to only 20% for the SHJ cells. The cell interconnect ribbons were attached by a silver-based ECA, which was clearly more resistant to acid-induced corrosion than the lead-tin solder. This was also evident from the limited corrosion observed along silver fingers for all types of cells.

Fig. 5. Normalized maximum single-cell module power as a function of exposure time for three cell technologies (Al-BSF, PERC, and SHJ) in 1% acid at 60 °C without electrical bias. Inset shows FF for the same tests.

4. Applications to module development

Conventional tests for corrosion in PV modules, specifically the damp heat test, do not accurately reproduce field behavior [16,17]. This is because 1) the test conditions are not correlated to any realistic module operating conditions (extreme humidity), and 2) acetic acid is absent as a chemical stressor, except in extended testing. On these points the accelerated acid corrosion test developed in this work is aimed at more reliable assessment vis-à-vis long-term field performance of EVA encapsulated modules by probing this wear-out degradation mechanism. Moreover, the tests are much shorter, requiring up to a few hundred hours to achieve the same level of power loss seen in >3000 h (>125 days) of damp heat testing [1,11].

EVA remains the encapsulant of choice for most PV module manufacturers, in spite of the known challenges of environmental degradation, including acetic acid generation [7,23]. Additionally, the variety of solar cell, passivation, metallization, and interconnection technologies in the market is evolving and expanding very rapidly [23,24]. From the material side, there are major pushes towards reduced silver content and lead-free solders. It is already known that some lead-free solders are more susceptible to corrosion than lead-tin [20,21]. On the process side, there are continuous modifications to screen printing and soldering processes, and increased use of alternatives such as electroplating. Finally, in terms of cell design, there are an increasing number of busbars, new passivation layers, and bifacial concepts, while cutting, shingling, and back contacting of solar cells are also growing. While two busbars were standard up to ten years ago, it is now common to see 9+ busbars per cell. These then have a much smaller connection area with a higher surface to volume ratio, potentially making them more susceptible to corrosion. Concurrently, many solar cells are implementing use thin passivation layers to achieve higher efficiencies, and these may be susceptible to corrosion.

Thus, there are ample concerns about acetic acid corrosion in the foreseeable future that warrant improved testing, even if alternative encapsulants that do not generate acetic acid are slowly entering the market [23]. The accelerated corrosion test in this work requires the use of a release later to expose the cells, and is well suited to material and component (mini-module) testing to optimize materials and processes for improved corrosion resistance. Based on this work, two test conditions can be proposed. The first, to mimic expected field conditions, should be performed at 60 °C in 0.1% acid. These are conditions that can be expected in a 10 to 20 year-old PV module in a temperature climate [5,6,19]. This can also be extended up to 80 °C to simulate a desert or close-roof module installation. The second allows moderate acceleration (at least two times the first condition), and should be performed at 60 °C in 1% acid. In these conditions comparative analyses can be made between test specimens in a time frame of some days or a few weeks. Further improvements to this test method could include extraction of temperature dependencies (Arrhenius) for modelling purposes, and better understanding of the improved performance seen in biased solar cells.

5. Conclusions

Most module manufacturers will continue to use acid generating EVA encapsulants in the near-to mid-term. Moreover, there is a rapidly expanding variety of materials, processes, and designs used in solar cell, passivation, metallization, and interconnection technologies. Thus, an accelerated acid corrosion test to probe wear-out degradation behavior has great relevance to module development. In that regard, in this work an accelerated corrosion test method was developed with major improvements on damp heat testing. In a few hundred hours it achieves the same level of power degradation that takes >3000 h in a damp heat test. The tests to failure included immersion of half-laminated solar cells (front-side exposed) in acetic acid baths of varying concentration, temperature, and cell bias. High acid concentrations (>1%), resulted in

rapid degradation due to ribbon detachment. Higher temperatures accelerated module power loss by several times, mostly by fill factor reduction, and features matched those seen in field modules with corrosion-related degradation. The application of electrical bias initially led to a drop in current, but eventually these cells outperformed non-biased cells. Finally, SHJ cells were more resistant to corrosion effects than Al-BSF and PERC cells, a behavior likely related to the use of a silver-based ECA for cell interconnection. An optimized test can be used to screen and improve design for a variety of solar cell, passivation, metallization, and interconnection technologies that are susceptible to corrosion.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Andrew Fairbrother: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Luca Gnocchi:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation. **Christophe Ballif:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition. **Alessandro Virtuani:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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